

Reinforced Model Predictive Guidance and Control for Spacecraft Proximity Operations

Lorenzo Capra^{*1}, Andrea Brandonisio¹, Michèle Lavagna¹

¹*Politecnico di Milano, Aerospace Science and Technology Dept, Via la Masa 34, 20156 Milan, Italy*

An increased level of autonomy is attractive above all in the framework of proximity operations and researchers are focusing more and more on artificial intelligence techniques to improve spacecrafts capabilities in these scenarios. This work presents an autonomous AI-based guidance algorithm to plan the sub-optimal path of a chaser spacecraft for the map reconstruction of an artificial uncooperative target, coupled with Model Predictive Control for the tracking of the trajectory generated. Deep Reinforcement Learning is particularly interesting for enabling spacecrafts autonomous guidance, since this problem can be formulated as a Partially Observable Markov Decision Process, and because it leverages well domain randomization to cope with model uncertainty, thanks to the Neural Networks generalizing capabilities. The main drawback of this method is that it is difficult to verify its optimality mathematically, and the constraints can be added only as part of the objective function, so it is not guaranteed that the solution satisfies them. To this aim a convex Model Predictive Control formulation is employed to track the RL-based trajectory, while simultaneously enforcing compliance with the constraints. This algorithm is extensively tested in an end-to-end AI-based pipeline with image-generation in the loop, and the results are presented.

1 Introduction

In recent years, space research is increasingly shifting towards the enhancement of the on-board spacecrafts' autonomy for all kind of missions, such as on-orbit servicing activities. In-orbit service and proximity operations may include a broad range of different activities, among which the autonomous guidance and control of a chaser spacecraft around an uncooperative and unknown space object. The work here presented develops an innovative adaptive guidance algorithm for the path-planning of the chaser's trajectory around an uncooperative artificial object, aiming to the shape and map reconstruction of the latter via imaging. In this context, the spacecraft au-

tonomously explores the surrounding environment and plans the following actions to take. Thus, the problem falls in the Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) framework, and since the planning operations is also performed, it is called active. SLAM may be phrased as a Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP), which entails an agent interacting with the environment and exchanging information with it. The goal is to solve for the decision-making policy of the agent, and to do so Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques are employed. Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithms are a powerful tool when dealing with decision-making problems and the combination with Neural Networks in DRL allows to improve the generalizing capabilities of the resulting policy, as they leverage well domain randomization to cope with model uncertainty. Several works have already underlined some of the beneficial effects of machine learning tools to spacecraft guidance and control enhancement as treated in [1] [2], and applications of deep reinforcement learning have been already analyzed in different scenarios and environments. Multiple contributions have been studied in [3], [4] and [5] by Gaudet, Linares and Furfaro, where both planetary landing and close proximity operations were investigated. This work builds upon previous research on the topic in [6] and [7], where DRL for relative guidance is tested extensively. The main drawbacks of AI-based methods for performing these tasks are the complexity in validating the results and providing a mathematical proof for the optimal solution. Some recent works deals with the stability of dynamical systems controlled via Neural Networks [8] [9], but more research is to be performed. When dealing with constrained optimization problems, the regions of the solution space that the agent cannot explore are only defined as part of the objective function, and as such, it is not guaranteed that the optimal decision-making always respects them. For an autonomous system this is quite a problem, so the proposed method to solve it is to combine the gener-

^{*}Corresponding author. E-Mail: lorenzo.capra@polimi.it

alizing capabilities and adaptivity of Reinforcement Learning with the capability to enforce constraints in the optimization of Model Predictive Control. This is the main innovative aspect of the work, the combination of the advantages of both RL and MPC, as done in [10], but still rather unexplored in the space GNC field. The resulting algorithm maintains the advantages of learning-based methods by optimizing a non-differentiable task-level objective, as well as allowing the optimization on a cumbersome objective function such as the map reconstruction one, while simultaneously enforcing compliance with the constraints when tracking the DRL generated trajectory with MPC, which offers precise actuation and ease in constraints handling. Measures like this are essential for achieving safe AI usage in space. The proposed solution is tested to verify its performances on an end-to-end AI-based simulator with image generation in the loop, tuned for proximity operations with an uncooperative target.

2 Problem statement

The work proposes an innovative decision-making process to autonomously plan the pseudo-optimal guidance around an uncooperative space object, that is TANGO for this case study, with Deep Reinforcement Learning. This is coupled with Model Predictive Control, which optimizes the trajectory to minimize the difference with the DRL one, while enforcing both action and state constraints. The overall pipeline describing such approach is reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Reinforced Model Predictive Guidance and Control scheme.

The input fed into the DRL agent is estimated in the image processing and navigation blocks, which returns realistic errors and noise in the filtered state.

The autonomous guidance agent then crafts the guidance policy to maximize the reward function, and it is propagated online for a specified timespan, equal to the prediction horizon of the Model Predictive Controller. The generated trajectory in this time frame is then passed to the MPC optimizer, which returns the control actions the spacecraft should perform to adhere to the guidance while respecting constraints. The two main components are described in the next sections.

2.1 DRL Guidance

Reinforcement Learning is a widely employed tool for solving MDPs [11], and its combination with Neural Networks, pioneered by [12], for function approximation, allows to solve many complex problems characterized by high-dimensionality and partial observability. A state-of-the-art Deep Reinforcement Learning algorithm, Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [13], solves for the spacecraft decision-making policy. Three main characters emerge from the decision-making problem: the state, the agent policy, and the reward function.

State space. It is the set of information coming from the image processing and navigation algorithms. The state vector fed to the agent should be tailored in such a way that it contains only essential information for the decision-making process, to build a policy capable of selecting the appropriate action in every condition the agent may find itself. The state space, defined in Eq. (1), comprises \mathbf{x} and $\dot{\mathbf{x}}$ which are the relative position and velocity between the spacecraft and the target object, and α and $\dot{\alpha}$ that are the relative angular position and velocity.

$$\mathcal{S} = [\mathbf{x}, \dot{\mathbf{x}}, \alpha, \dot{\alpha}] \tag{1}$$

Action space. The agent interacts with the surrounding environment, receiving the state observations and a reward signal and selecting accordingly the action to take. The action space here modeled assumes that the spacecraft can thrust in each of the six reference cartesian frame directions, namely $x, -x, y, -y, z, -z$. The option of null action is also available to the agent. This formulation renders a direct and continuous control on the trajectory, consistent with an active SLAM problem. The action space is defined in Eq. (2).

$$\mathcal{A} = [T_{x+}, T_{x-}, T_{y+}, T_{y-}, T_{z+}, T_{z-}, 0] \tag{2}$$

This kind of control action is generate by a *discrete* action space, that means an action space with a constrained number of possible options. To consider a

more realistic control action, a *continuous* action space may be defined; for a complete overview about this comparison, please refer to the study developed in [7].

A block scheme of the state-action interaction is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Policy neural network decision making.

The state vector S and the action vector A are the ones defined in Eq. (1) and Eq. (2). The selected internal dynamical model that is propagated is the one proposed in [14].

Reward function. The most significant and critical part of a DRL architecture is the definition of the reward model, whose maximization drives the learning behavior of the agent. In the context of this work, the goal is to achieve a high quality map of the target object together with a fast and safe process. The reward signals received by the agent are presented:

- **Map level score.** The faces that have both optimal Sun and camera exposition are the ones that generate an improvement in the level of the map. The maximum level defined for the map consists in having each faces photographed $N_{accuracy}$ times. Therefore, at each time step the map level, $MI_{\%}$, can be computed considering how many good photos of each face have been taken until that moment. The corresponding reward score is defined in Eq. (3) and, at each time step k the agent is rewarded for increasing the map level over the current value, $MI_{\%,k-1}$.

$$R_m = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } MI_{\%,k} > MI_{\%,k-1} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The improvement in the map depends on the Sun and camera incidence angles:

- **Sun incidence score.** The Sun incidence angle η is the angle between the Sun direction

relative to the target object and the normal to the face considered. The Sun incidence angle should be between $0^\circ - 70^\circ$, to avoid shadows or excessive brightness. Values outside that interval may correspond to conditions that degrade the quality of the image. If the angle exceeds this range, the photo can not be considered good enough to make a real improvement of the map.

- **Camera incidence score.** The camera incidence angle ε is intended as the angle between the normal to the face and the camera direction. This angle should be maintained between $5^\circ - 60^\circ$. Also in this case, if the angle exceeds this range, the photo can not be considered good enough to make a real improvement of the map.

- **Position score.** Negative scores are given when the spacecraft escapes from the region defined by a minimum and maximum distance from the target object, D_{min} and D_{max} .

$$R_d = \begin{cases} -100 & \text{if } d \leq D_{min} \text{ or } d \geq D_{max} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

2.2 MPC optimization

Model Predictive Control (MPC) combines the benefits of optimal and feedback control methods. Initially, it leverages system dynamics knowledge to solve an Optimal Control Problem (OCP) within a defined prediction horizon, discretized based on a chosen sampling step. Subsequently, the optimized control is implemented for a set number of time steps determined by the control horizon. MPC aims to find the best control action by solving an optimization problem at each time step, considering future predictions and constraints. While it can provide excellent performance and stability for many systems, several factors can affect its ability to guarantee optimal behavior, like model accuracy as well as too restrictive constraints or a system operating near them. After the control step on the dynamics block, the sequence in 1 is initiated once again, with the DRL agent providing the reference trajectory and the Model Predictive Control trying to optimize the control action to track it. One of the main advantages of using MPC is the straightforward implementation of constraints in the computation of the control action. Apart from the usual constraint on maximum spacecraft thrust, this work focuses on the implementation, in a convex form, of collision avoidance, as it cannot be guaranteed by the DRL guidance. The primary limitation of Model

Predictive Control lies in the computational time required to solve the optimal control problem at each time step, prompting the initial use of an analytic model. Moreover, convexifying the optimization cost function and constraints enables leveraging convex optimization solvers, thereby achieving a swift and effective solution suitable for autonomous control [15] [16]. The objective of the MPC is to find the control acceleration that minimizes a weighted function of tracking error, with respect to the trajectory generated by the DRL agent, and fuel cost.

3 Results

The Deep Reinforcement Learning agent is first trained offline, before deploying its decision-making policy in the entire GNC pipeline. A recurrent neural network architecture is selected to approximate the mapping function between the input state and the output actions, because of its improved stability when dealing with evolving dynamics with respect to simple Feed Forward Networks. Among the different types of RNN, this work exploits the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) recurrent layer. It is presented in Table 1.

Layer	Elements	Activation
LSTM Layers	24	-
1 st Hidden Layer (h1)	64	ReLU
2 nd Hidden Layer (h2)	32	ReLU
Learning rate	10 ⁻⁵	-

Table 1: Policy Recurrent Neural Network Architecture.

The training process is performed with randomized initial conditions regarding all the variables affecting the input state of the policy. This is done to stress the generalization capabilities of the neural network architecture, so to obtain an agent that can consistently perform well, whatever the initial conditions of the state variables are. For this reason, at the start of each episodic simulation run, they are randomly generated inside a certain range, reported in Table 2.

d and v are the relative position and velocity between the chaser and the target, α and δ represents the azimuth and the elevation angle respectively, and finally θ and $\dot{\theta}$ expresses the rotation angles and velocity of the target, with $i \in [1 : 3]$ specifying the axis. $D_{min} = 1.5m$ and $D_{max} = 35m$ are the two boundaries defining the possible stopping condition of an episode.

Both the actor and the critic networks models are

Variable	Range
d	$2D_{min} < d < 0.5D_{max}$
α	$0^\circ < \alpha < 360^\circ$
δ	$-90^\circ < \delta < 90^\circ$
v	$0 m/s$
θ_i	0°
$\dot{\theta}_i$	$-0.1 rad/s < \dot{\theta}_i < 0.1 rad/s$

Table 2: State variables initial condition ranges.

periodically updated during the training phase with an epoch of 10 episodes' trajectories, whose steps are divided in random batches of dimension 32. A single training episode terminates when the target object map is completely acquired or when the spacecraft's trajectory overcomes the region defined by the minimum and maximum distance from the target.

The hyperparameters of the DRL selected algorithm, that is PPO for its proven capabilities and state-of-the-art performance in several benchmark scenarios, are summarized in Table 3.

Variable	Value
Reward Discount Factor γ	0.99
Terminal Reward Discount Factor λ	0.95
Clipping Factor ϵ	0.2
Entropy Factor s_2	0.02
Optimizer	ADAM
Optimization Step frequency	10 episodes
Training episodes	18000

Table 3: PPO and training hyperparameters.

The results, in terms of episodic cumulative reward, average and episodic map level percentage and episode time are reported in Figure 3.

The profiles are increasing over time, meaning that the spacecraft is adjusting its decision-making towards an improved map reconstruction and it is able to remain inside the specified region of space for longer. Once the training phase is concluded, the outcoming policy network is tested to understand the effective performance in nominal conditions. The main metrics to verify the learning-based policy are reported in Table 4. Notably, the average map level obtained by the agent is almost 87%.

Once trained, the agent is inserted in the overall simulator architecture and coupled with the convex MPC formulation with the collision avoidance con-

Figure 3: TANGO case study training of the DRL agent: metrics (reward score, map level, episode time) evolution along the simulation.

Average Score	406.4
Average Map	86.6 %
Average Time	6.6 h
Average Thrusting	22.6

Table 4: Average testing results of RL guidance.

straint. This constraint is set to $5m$, that is a higher value with respect to the one used to design the RL reward function, to verify the correctness of the complete guidance and control algorithm. An example trajectory from a random simulation is reported in Figure 4. As visible, the MPC tracks correctly the trajectory generated by the DRL agent, except when the latter comes too close to the target. When this happens, the optimization enforces the collision avoidance constraint which then shapes the trajectory to remain outside of the boundary region, ensuring safe operations.

A new testing campaign is performed on the high-fidelity simulator, to check the robustness of the algorithm against noise and uncertainty coming from the image processing and navigation blocks, providing the input state, and the mapping level with the trajectory imposed by the MPC following the DRL guidance. Different noise levels are tested, up to $12dB$ for the image generation step, leading to a compounding error from image processing and navigation lower than 5% in relative range and 5° in mean angular error. The results are reported in Table 5.

Figure 4: Example trajectory of RL guidance + MPC.

Average Map	84.3 %
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Table 5: Results of RL guidance with MPC control.

4 Discussion

The proposed work deals with an adaptive guidance and control algorithm to autonomously reconstruct the geometry and shape of the selected uncooperative artificial object in space. The guidance block is implemented with a state-of-the-art Deep Reinforcement Learning algorithm to design the decision-making policy of the spacecraft agent. RL can directly optimize a task-level objective and can leverage domain randomization to cope with model uncertainty, allowing the discovery of more robust control responses. This method's primary limitation lies in the challenge of mathematically confirming its optimality and the inability to directly incorporate constraints outside the objective function, thus potentially leading to solutions that don't fully meet the constraints. To address this, a convex Model Predictive Control framework is utilized to follow the RL-derived trajectory while ensuring adherence to the constraints. The overall pipeline results in terms of average map reconstruction are consistent with the performance of the RL guidance, but this time collision avoidance with the target is ensured by MPC.

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